

SECURITY MEN PERCEPTION OF CRIMINAL PROFILING ON CRIME CONTROL IN KEFFI POLICE DIVISIONAL HEADQUARTERS NASARAWA STATE NIGERIA

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Abstract

Crime control encompasses a wide range of proactive measures aimed at reducing crime rates and enhancing public safety. It is on these bases that this study investigated the security men perception of criminal profiling on crime control in Keffi Police Divisional Headquarters of Nasarawa State. The study employed cross sectional survey design using purposive sampling technique to select one hundred and thirty (130) participants. Two hypotheses were postulated and the data collated in the study and the interpretation of the analysis. The stated hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to test the relationship between the variables, Independent Sample t-test to test the gender difference. Hypothesis one result revealed a no statistically significant negative relationship between criminal profiling and crime control among security men in Keffi (128) = -0.201 , $P > 0.05$. In other words, the hypothesis was not confirmed in this study. Hypothesis two the result revealed a no statistically significant t (128) = -0.508 , $P > 0.05$ difference between male and female on the perception of criminal profiling and crime control among the security men in Keffi. In other words, the hypothesis was not confirmed in this study. We concluded and recommended that, there is no statistically significant negative relationship between criminal profiling and crime control among security men in Keffi. The security personnel especially the police should be trained in the aspect of criminal profiling since is a new technique in controlling crime in our society so as to be conversant with the technique.

Keywords: Security Men Perception of Criminal Profiling on Crime Control

Introduction

Controlling the occurrence of an illness is easier and health wise better than searching for a cure and curbing its detrimental effects. This age old wisdom makes similar sense in the case of crime. Violence and crime is very similar to an epidemic of a contagious disease. Incidents of crime and violence not only impact an individual but also the community (Fagin, 2020). Crime control is a broad area that encompasses a great many programs and initiatives. A great diversity of crimes can be the target of crime control and different approaches to crime control target different factors contributing to crime. Consequently, a diversity of actors will frequently be engaged in efforts to control crime. This can range from international agencies such as the United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime, to national crime control bodies, down to local actors.

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Crime control encompasses a wide range of proactive measures aimed at reducing crime rates and enhancing public safety. These strategies can be broadly categorized into situational, social, and community-based approaches. Focuses on modifying the immediate environment to reduce opportunities for crime. Examples include improved lighting in high-crime areas, security cameras, and target hardening measures such as locks and alarms. Emphasizes reducing the likelihood of criminal acts by making potential targets less attractive or accessible to offenders.

Government, non-government, civil society, voluntary, activist, private sector and individual citizens can engage in crime control activities (UNODC, 2020) which can produces many positive outcomes. It is not strange to come across crime committed especially violent ones such as murder, rape, arson and terrorism with little or no material evidence directly linking the suspect to the crime thereby making it difficult for the law enforcement to investigate and apprehend the likely offenders and identification of victims. The situation necessitated the law enforcement as well as forensic psychologists and analysts to delve into crime scene analysis to find out patterns, mode of operation, traces, signature, victimology and patterns to aid in identifying the likely offender (Ann, 2021).

Within the last two decades, Nigeria has been experiencing a new wave of crimes ranging from gruesome murder, aggravated rape, rural banditry, kidnapping and other form of organized crime (Ogechi & Oluwa, 2019). The way and manner these crimes are perpetrated in Nigeria recently, has rendered traditional crime investigation techniques unproductive and ineffective. Criminal profiling is a tool used by law enforcement agencies to help solve crimes. The purpose is not to identify a specific individual who is the likely offender, but to narrow down a pool of suspects by determining certain characteristics the offender is likely to have. The profile helps law enforcement agencies track down a suspect, or is released to the public to enlist help with determining the identity of the offender (Ainsworth, 2019).

Nowadays profiling rests, sometimes uneasily, somewhere between law enforcement and psychology. As a science, it is still a relatively new field with few set boundaries or definitions. The control or nonoccurrence of some future criminal incident reduces the human costs for victims of crime. Lives can be saved, physical harm can be controlled, and financial lost can be minimized. For this reason, crime control is very attractive to many governments and other groups, and it is the reason why crime control has become an important area of policy and practice (UNODC, 2020). However, crime control is not without problems. Its practitioners don't always agree on methodology or even terminology. Since its emergence, criminal profiling has

been given several different terms to describe the technique (Maurice, 2020). For instance, **ISSN: 2971-7760, Vol: 3, Number: 3, Date: 11/11/2025** psychological profiling, criminal profiling, criminal personality profiling, criminal investigative analysis, and behavioral evidence profiling. Regardless, though, of the descriptive label applied, profiling as investigative tool today is entirely intuitive based and represents a less than educated attempt to provide law enforcement agencies with detailed information about the behaviour of an unknown individual who has committed a crime. For example, most published accounts of profiling, which details the methods employed by various individuals, have tended to take the form of semi-autobiographical books and journalistic articles rather than systematic academic work and, hence, are difficult to evaluate from an accuracy or scientific point of view (Maurice, 2020).

As such, the one major flaw of current profiling methods is that most of all profiles emphasize the various psychological functions that murder has for the offender not what varieties of action the murder actually consists of. Consequently, these profiles make little distinction between the overt crime scene behaviours as they occur in murders and the psycho-dynamic processes that are taken to account for or produce that behavior. Hence, there is little attempt by profilers to differentiate between aspects of the offender's motivations and life-style from aspects of his offending behaviour.

Godwin (2002) concluded that, "On the whole, criminal profiling methods are inherently flawed due to weak operational definitions and inferred deductive assumptions made about offender actions and characteristics. In its present form, this leads to empirically unsound and misleading profiles". While Godwin believes that the reason why profiles can be misleading is because of frail definitions within methods and not such concrete techniques which ultimately result in misleading profiles, others believe that the profiles are not made specific enough which could lead law enforcement professionals in any direction. As cited by Ian (2010), "In many cases, offender profiles are as vague as to be meaningless, according to psychologist Craig (2008). At best, they have little impact on murder investigations; at worst they risk misleading investigators and waste police time, he said". Another aspect that could negatively affect the development of a profile is what is called the false recognition effect. Also, according to Craig (2008), "Research has convincingly demonstrated that people often have memories for things that they have never actually experienced". At times when suspects are involved, they are relied upon to convey as much information as they can about the offender as well as the crime.

Again, as stated in Craig (2008) study demonstrated that problems might occur when profiles are

not properly documented, including a small amount of forgetting and a significant amount of false recognition". If these results were based on a real crime that needed a suspect's profile, this could result in negative consequences that would be harmful to the case. As a result of all this skepticism, the method of criminal profiling is not generally accepted in the court of law. This presents a major issue when a developed profile of an offender is considered as the main evidence in a case.

Ultimately, criminal profiling should still be used within criminal cases as a method to assist in determining the offender. However, it should not be used as the primary means since it does not yet appear to be as reliable, valid and accurate as it could be. Further advancements should be done with criminal profiling in order for it to become a more solid method. Criminal profiling does appear to have a lot of potential in helping solve cases, if it undergoes some development and is used in the right way.

A very crucial criticism of criminal profiling is the fact that there are no much studies showing or demonstrating the techniques of profiling to be dependable and valid. "The majority of the 152 police psychologists surveyed by Bartol (2019) reported that they were skeptical about the validity and usefulness of profiling." (Cook & Hinman, 2019). There has been a lot of skepticism towards criminal profiling (Krylova, 2021). Many believe that it is more of a skill rather than a science that can be seen as reliable, valid and accurate. However just like any other scientific method it does have its flaws, which is what is making it difficult for people to believe that it is of any help in solving crimes.

Kocsis (2007) according to him posits that the bulk of extant literature surrounding it nonetheless remains oriented toward being a technique aimed at assisting in the investigation of intractable crimes most often of an atypical violent nature among those who see gender differences across these various realms, there is no clear consensus about whether these differences are primarily rooted in biology or in societal expectations (Kim et al., 2017). In other words, nature and nurture accounts may account for difference in gender perception (Prentice & Carranza, 2002). However, profiling from a true behavioral approach considers the individual differences between offenses (not offenders) by looking at crime scene actions that can be observed rather than guess at the individual's internal workings or motivations for the crime. Numerous TV programmes and documentaries have also in recent times focused around the assertion of criminal profiling, including Millennium, profiler and even The X-Files (Muller, 2020).

The urgent need to deal with the recent surge in crimes within the last two decades has generated a sense of fear and anxiety among the populace in view of the limited capacity of the law enforcement to apprehend offenders which is caused by a number of limiting factors such as inadequate trained personnel (experts), poor equipment, little or no data base, inadequate forensic laboratories and limited access to technological tools and advancement in Nigeria. Crimes such as kidnap, abduction, rape, murder, cybercrime and terrorism have tremendously advanced in terms of how they are committed. The archaic and anachronistic traditional eyewitnesses' account and confession ways of investigating crimes by the Nigeria law enforcement agencies have proven ineffective and inefficient (Juliet & Moses, 2019).

Inadequate knowledge and awareness of effective methods and techniques to be applied by the law enforcement is clearly evident considering how criminals or suspects are being handled in Nigeria. Effective and reliable methods and techniques should be given priority considering the complex and sensitive nature of crime control in the society and optimum utilization of resources available. Advanced countries such as the United States of America has one of the most effective crime control measures in place because they are always willing to adopt various techniques that will aid control, detection and investigation of crime (Ann, 2021).

These problems pose a great obstacle to law enforcement agencies' function of detecting and investigating crime. In simple terms, the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) particularly and other law enforcement agencies are obviously finding it difficult to live up to their expectations in curtailing the new wave of violent crimes across the country. In recent times, Nigeria has been featured in a lot of unpleasant headlines in both local and international media bordering of criminality and lack effective and productive investigative and other crime control techniques in combating the menace holding the African most populous nation to ransom (Juliet & Moses, 2019).

Security men has always relied on psychology, whether detectives are trying to understand a suspect's motives or jury consultants are helping to select jurors. In recent years, the role of psychology in security men has become even more critical. Thanks to advances in neuroscience and psychological research, police officers and detectives now have a better understanding of how criminals think and how to solve crimes. For example, detectives can now use psychological profiling to understand a suspect's mindset better and predict their behaviour. This information

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can generate investigation leads or narrow the pool of suspects. Similarly, police officers receive training in psychology to help them deal with difficult situations, such as hostage negotiations or managing people with mental illnesses. Security men personnel are better equipped to solve crimes and keep the public safe by understanding human behaviour.

It is generally assumed that anybody within the society is a potential suspect of a crime. Therefore, when the characteristics or profile of the likely offender is known then the whole scope of investigation is then narrowed down to the profile or characteristics that it is pointing towards. In simple terms, criminal profile seeks to aid investigation by narrowing down its scope to facilitate easy apprehension of offenders.

The collaboration between law enforcement and psychological professionals is essential for effectively addressing the complex challenges of crime control, offender rehabilitation, and community safety. The study seeks to create more awareness to authorities concerned and the general public on criminal profiling and forensic assessment tool on crime control and how it can be utilized.

Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following questions;

- i. What is the perception of the security men on crime control in Keffi?
- ii. Will there be gender difference in perception of criminal profiling towards crime control among the security men in Keffi?

Objectives of the Study

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- i. To assess the perception of the security men on crime control in Keffi.
- ii. To ascertain the gender difference in perception of criminal profiling towards crime control among security men in Keffi.

Hypotheses

The following statement of hypotheses was tested:

- i. There will be a significant relationship between perceptions of security men on crime control in Keffi.
- ii. There will be a significant gender difference in the perception of criminal profiling towards crime control among the security men in Keffi.

The study employed cross sectional survey design. The design allowed the researcher to study variables as they are without creating artificial situations. Across sectional survey design, sought to identify the relationship between the two variables. This was considered appropriate for this study as the variables involved in the study were not manipulated but considered retrospectively in the way they occurred. When survey design is employed, an excellent method of descriptive prediction is achieved. The researcher involved participants in which questionnaires were distributed in other to collect information on the variables that matter in the study.

Participants

The participants for this study included all the one hundred and fifty (150) Officers of the Nigeria Police Force (Keffi LGA Divisional Headquarters Nasarawa State Command). The targeted location(s) of the participants Keffi Divisional Headquarters. Out of the one hundred and fifty questionnaires distributed, one hundred and thirty (130) were valid and analyst. The demographic characteristics of officers from Nigerian Police Force were described respectively .Participants male were (85; 65.4%) while female were (45; 34.6%). Age 18-22 years (3; 2.3%), 23-27 years (13; 10%), 28-32 year (51; 39.2%), 33-37 years (45; 34.6%), 38-42 years (15; 11.6%), 43-47 years (2; 1.5%) 48above (1; 0.8%) Marital Status: Married (92; 70.7%), Single (38; 29.2%). Educational Status: Primary School (13; 10%), Secondary School (74; 56.9%), Tertiary Institution (43; 33.1%).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sampling technique that was employed in this study was purposive sampling technique considering the nature of the setting and work schedules. According to Joan (2009), purposive sampling technique is a method that allows each member of the population to be selected as participants. This technique was adopted so as to permit participation of all Police Officers to enable an effective and accurate analysis. Henceforth, the study adopted total population as the sample size. The refer unit of analysis for this study consists of personnel in Keffi Division of Nasarawa State, from age 18 and above. The participants (Police Officers) by this method were constitute a good representation of law enforcement personnel. Because the population is not large enough for selection of sample. The research therefore used the total sample.

A 21-item standardized developed questionnaire was adopted by the researcher. The questionnaire was developed by Agashua et al. (2019) to assess participant's experience on criminal profiling and Forensic Assessment tools as regards to crime control in Nigeria. It was divided into 4 parts comprising 5-items on each part. The first part is bordering on participant's bio data, second part to assess participant's knowledge of criminal profiling, the third part assess the participant's experience on criminal profiling while the last part assessed effectiveness of criminal profiling. The questionnaire is scored in five (5) point scales of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Undecided (UD), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) for the first and yes or no for the third and fourth part. The Psychometric property of the instrument revealed a Split-Half reliability method was adopted. The results revealed a Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient for the two-half as 0.742 and 0.664 respectively with a Guttman Split-Half Reliability Coefficient of 0.753.

Procedure

The researcher wrote a letter of introduction to the authority where the research was conducted and thereafter, proceeds to distribute the questionnaires and explains how the instrument was used to get the required information. Ethical considerations were dully observed as there was no force and were allowed to voluntarily participate, keeping confidentiality to boost their confidence. Duly filled questionnaires were returned to the researcher upon completion by the participants for further analysis.

Statistics Used

The data gathered from the participants through the use of questionnaire was analyzed by using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Analysis will be carried out using descriptive statistics, which will help generate frequency and simple percentage distribution, mean score value and standard deviation. The hypotheses were further analysed using inferential statistics for the test of Hypotheses. Pearson Product-moment Correlation was used to test the relationship between the variables and Independent Sample-t-test was used to test the difference between male and female officers perception of criminal profiling.

Results

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There will be a significant relationship between positive perception of security men on criminal profiling and crime control in Keffi. This hypothesis was tested with Pearson Product-Moment Correlation in table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Result Showing Relationship between Positive Perception of the Security Men on Criminal Profiling and Crime Control in Keffi.

Variables	M	SD	df	r	Sig.
Perception of Security Men	9.88	2.668	128	-0.201	0.003
Crime Control	17.11	1.139			

$r(128) = -0.201, P < 0.05$

Table 1 shows the summary results of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation between positive perception of the security men on criminal profiling and crime control. The results revealed the mean and standard deviation scores for perception of the security men on criminal profiling (M= 9.88, SD= 2.668) and crime control (M= 17.11, SD= 1.139). Further analysis revealed a no statistically significant positive relationship between criminal profiling and crime control among security men in Keffi $r(128) = -0.201, P > 0.05$. In other words, the hypothesis was not confirmed in this study.

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Hypothesis 2: There will be a significant gender difference in the perception of criminal profiling towards crime control among the security men in Keffi. This hypothesis was tested with Independent Sample t-test in table 2

Table 2: Summary of Result Showing Gender difference between Perception of Criminal Profiling towards Crime Control.

Gender	N	M	SD	df	t	Sig.
Males	85	22.118	4.001	128	-.508	.407
Females	45	22.533	4.649			

$t(128) = -.508, P > 0.05$

Table 2 shows the difference in the mean scores between males and female where male security

men (M= 42.64; SD= 9.757) and female security men (M= 22.533; SD= 4.649 on criminal control). In addition, the result revealed a no statistically significant $t(128) = -.508, P > 0.05$ difference between male and female on the perception of criminal profiling and crime control among the security men in Keffi. In other words, the hypothesis was not confirmed in this study.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the security men perception of criminal profiling on crime control in Keffi Police Divisional Headquarters of Nasarawa State. Two hypotheses were postulated and the data collated in the study and the interpretation of the analysis. The data was analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. The descriptive statistics used were Frequency, percentages, means and standard deviations while the inferential statistics used to test the stated hypotheses were Pearson Product Moment Correlation to test the relationship between the variables, Independent Sample t-test to test the gender difference. The first hypothesis was not confirmed as statistically significant; therefore, we concluded that there is a statistically significant negative relationship between criminal profiling and crime control among security men in Keffi.

The second hypothesis was not confirmed in the study; therefore we concluded that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female on the perception of criminal profiling and crime control among the security men in Keffi. The study assesses security men perception of criminal profiling on crime control in Keffi Police Divisional Headquarters Nasarawa State Nigeria. The study will employ survey design. The design will allow the researcher to study variables as they are without creating artificial situations. The sampling technique that was employed in this study was a purposive sampling technique considering the nature of the setting and work schedules. Two hypotheses were stated and tested.

The first hypothesis stated that there will be a significant relationship between positive perception of the security men on criminal profiling and crime control in Keffi. This hypothesis was tested with Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. The result further analysis revealed a no statistically significant negative relationship between criminal profiling and crime control among security men in Keffi. In other words, the hypothesis was not confirmed in this study. Supporting the finding of this study, Godwin (2002) concluded that, "On the whole, criminal profiling methods are inherently flawed due to weak operational definitions and inferred deductive assumptions made about offender actions and characteristics. In its present form, this leads to empirically unsound and misleading profiles". While Godwin believes that the reason why

profiles can be misleading is because of frail definitions within methods and not such concrete techniques which ultimately result in misleading profiles, others believe that the profiles are not made specific enough which could lead law enforcement professionals in any direction. As cited by Ian Sample (2010), “In many cases, offender profiles are as vague as to be meaningless, according to psychologist Craig (2008). At best, they have little impact on murder investigations; at worst they risk misleading investigators and waste police time, he said”. Another aspect that could negatively affect the development of a profile is what is called the false recognition effect. Also, according to Craig (2008), “Research has convincingly demonstrated that people often have memories for things that they have never actually experienced”. At times when suspects are involved, they are relied upon to convey as much information as they can about the offender as well as the crime.

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Ultimately, criminal profiling should still be used within criminal cases as a method to assist in determining the offender. However, it should not be used as the primary means since it does not yet appear to be as reliable, valid and accurate as it could be. Further advancements should be done with criminal profiling in order for it to become a more solid method. Criminal profiling does appear to have a lot of potential in helping solve cases, if it undergoes some development and is used in the right way.

A very crucial criticism of criminal profiling is the fact that there are no much studies showing or demonstrating the techniques of profiling to be dependable and valid. “The majority of the 152 police psychologists surveyed by Bartol (2019) reported that they were skeptical about the validity and usefulness of profiling.” (Cook & Hinman, 2019). There has been a lot of skepticism towards criminal profiling (Krylova, 2021). Many believe that it is more of a skill rather than a science that can be seen as reliable, valid and accurate. However just like any other scientific method it does have its flaws, which is what is making it difficult for people to believe that it is of any help in solving crimes.

The second hypotheses stated that there will be a significant gender difference in the perception of criminal profiling towards crime control among the security men in Keffi. This hypothesis was tested with Independent Sample t-test. The result revealed a no statistically significant difference between male and female on the perception of criminal profiling and crime control among the security men in Keffi. In other words, the hypothesis was not confirmed in this study. In accordance with the finding of this study, Kocsis (2007) according to him posits that the bulk of extant literature surrounding it nonetheless remains oriented toward being a technique aimed at assisting in the investigation of intractable crimes most often of an atypical violent nature among those who see gender differences across these various realms, there is no clear consensus about whether these differences are primarily rooted in biology or in societal expectations (Kim et al., 2017). In other words, nature and nurture accounts may account for difference in gender perception (Prentice & Carranza, 2002).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study regarding security men perception of criminal profiling on crime control. The study confirmed that there was a statistically significant negative relationship between criminal profiling and crime control among security men in Keffi Nasarawa State. Also, that there was no statistically significant difference between male and female on the perception of criminal profiling and crime control among the security men in Keffi.

Recommendations

At the end of the study, we recommended the following: That

- i. The security personnel especially the police should be trained in the aspect of criminal profiling since is a new technique in controlling crime in our society so as to be conversant with the technique.
- ii. Holistic approach in crime control should be inculcated in police training manual to acquaint the personnel during operation or while trying to control crime.
- iii. It is needful to continue doing research in the line of other studies that we may obtain more information on certain forensic psychological way of crime control

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